

INTERNATIONAL STUDIES ON QUALITY ASSESSMENT OF EDUCATION

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Annotation: International Studies is an international program to assess student literacy in which Uzbekistan works for the first time. It is important in this that students can apply the knowledge gained in life-in what daroja in a real situation. In the past 20 years, this type of International Studies has become a program that gives rise to the main criteria and educational institutions that have studied the effectiveness, quality of public education.

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In recent years, organizations implemented in mamalakatımız have created economy that has studied growth information to increase the demand for qualified personnel and maturity specialists in all areas.

This in itself requires an increase in the characteristics of our teachers 'interest in classes and an increase in teachers' attention to all-round educational upbringing.

The reason is that in the 20th century and before, when strong memory, encyclopedic knowledge, specialists who knew as much information as possible in their field were highly capable, now this knowledge has become decisive. Excellent online databases were created by search engines, online encyclopedias, fields, so that now the need to remember this information has fallen to the second level. In a modern professional, it is the competence to analyze knowledge, to be able to generate new data from them, to see in folk language "What Cup under the Cup", first of all

Because, the main task of education is to manage what is needed today and in the future for a successful life in a Learned Society. For this creative thought today is an important consideration that young people should have. This vision shows them adapting to a world that has criticized workers with "21st-century" visions in addition to simple questioning, which is changing in the way and intensity they relate to. In general, in the future, which we read today, working in areas that are not even available now, waiting for new problems to be solved behind new technologies. Provides an opportunity to support in an unusual way the local and global problems that need to be applied for the purchase of a thinking program at the place of study

The fact that the above requirements are very important for the educational system, like most foreign countries, is that the development of the educational and scientific fields of assessment and monitoring provides information about the dialogue aimed at improving the quality of Secondary Education.[3]

To this end, the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan adopted Resolution No. 997 on December 8, 2018, establishing international relations in the field of assessment of the quality of education in the Republican public education system, establishing international relations, R & D and innovative activities of teachers and young people, and above all, comprehensive support of creative activities and creativity of the younger generation.

Following the decision, the organization of international research on international assessment programs was established below:

1. Progress in international reading and literacy learning (PIRLS) - Elementary 4th grade students to assess the level of reading and understanding of the text;
2. International areas of study of mathematics and science (TIMSS) -4 and 8th grade teaching for the use of mathematics and natural path subjects;
3. International Student Assessment Program (PISA) -15-year-old education,

to assess the level of literacy in mathematics and natural path subjects;

4. International study of education and training (education) - for the study of the environment of teaching and learning in general secondary educational institutions of the executive and pedagogical personnel;

For international research on the above international assessment programs, the state inspectorate for quality control of education is now the National Center for quality assessment of Education's main tasks and areas of activity have been identified.

Extra-budgetary pension fund under the Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan;

the development and recruitment of innovative methods for the development of literacy in the educational system of reading, mathematics and natural path Sciences to carry out established scientific research;

establishing international relations in the field of quality assessment of education, developing and practically enhancing international projects, organizing and conducting international scientific conferences and symposia processing;

transition to basic and Applied Research in the field of assessment of the quality of Education.

scientific and practical support of research on quality assessment of Education;

Ensuring the successful implementation of international research on educational areas of the OSCE;

Accounting of states established in international assessment programs of the Republic of Uzbekistan accounting of other states;

Increase the income and profitability of the extra-budgetary pension fund under the Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan increase the profitability of the extra-budgetary pension fund under the Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan;

preparation of recommendations for improving the skills of pedagogical personnel on reading, mathematics and fans on the natural path using innovative teaching methods.

For this, until February 1, 2019, qad., Together with the National Center, one strict task was set for the development of a development program to provide processing in international assessment programs and competitions for the identification and development of teachers from the 1st grade in general educational areas.

Changes and additions to the content of reading, mathematics and natural way science reading programs and reading etiquette based on the results of International Studies;

Building a national base of questions on assessment programs of International Studies and integrating them into reading programs;

Student literacy assessment improvement of the national system and analysis of practical skills in 2019-2021 qualitative delivery of tests considered assessment;

Creation of additional methodological manuals and literature on the basis of training programs that contain questions on assessment programs of international research;

The Republic of Karakalpakstan, centers of Regions and Tashkent City are aimed at carrying out international research in each district (city);

Responding to scientific research on programs for international assessment of talented pedagogical personnel in general secondary education issues;

Cooperation of general secondary educational institutions with modern information and communication tools and inventory of the state of connection to the world information network of the Internet, as well as taking measures to eliminate existing problems;

-To the Ministry of Higher and secondary special education of the Republic of Uzbekistan to make changes and additions to the educational programs of higher educational institutions, training and retraining of specialists in the fields of Public Education, Mathematics and Natural Sciences based on the results of International Studies.

-Based on the content and essence of the program of International Studies, State Scientific and technical programs are carried out.

The timely and high-quality implementation of the above tasks ensured the integration of the educational system of our mamalakat with the international educational process, allows teachers to leave and develop adults of the XXI century, in the future their conscious choice of profession, independent life and find their place as an active citizen in society.

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